

ARE YOU FALLING OFF THE SAP ERP CLIFF? An Executive Briefing Paper

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Executive Summary

SAP (System Analysis Program) is a global leader in Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems. SAP is ending support for its legacy Enterprise Central Component (ECC) platform by 2027. Their clients need to move to the new S/4HANA² system.

As a transition, this presents significant challenges, including potential operational disruptions, data losses, compliance risks, and increased costs. The UK's largest employers, like the NHS, Tesco, Compass Group, Sainsbury's and Amazon, will be checking their own legacy data systems, and their suppliers'.

Failure to migrate successfully could result in loss of vendor support, security vulnerabilities, and hinder future business growth. This briefing paper emphasizes the need for careful planning and provides key questions for executives to consider when preparing for this critical transition. There is also a list of companies that could assist you in this or other similar projects.

Introduction

Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems are crucial for modern businesses. By integrating various functions, they help enable efficient operations, including an enhanced user/customer experience (UX/CX). SAP, a pioneer in this field, has been a dominant player for decades. However, as technology evolves, SAP is guiding its customers towards a new era with its S/4HANA platform.

This briefing paper aims to alert Senior Managers and other Executives to the risks associated with the end of support for legacy SAP products and the urgent need to plan for migration to avoid potential business disruptions.

What is Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP)?

ERP systems are a suite of data gathering, storage, management and analysis software that together enable business planning, decision making and reporting. ERP often includes Supply Chain Management (SCM) and Customer Relationship Management (CRM). Three of the biggest and best-known ERP Systems are SAP, Oracle NetSuite and Microsoft Dynamics 365 Business Central.³ ERP Systems are increasingly cloud based and are being adopted by smaller companies compared to previously.

In this Executive Briefing Paper, we are focussing on the SAP ERP. The purpose of this paper is an alert to all Senior Managers and Chief Executives on the potential risks to your organisational data when support for legacy SAP products are withdrawn in the coming years.

ERP FUNCTION	DESCRIPTION
Data Gathering	Collecting data from various business processes
Data Storage	Securely storing collected data
Data Management	Organizing and maintaining data for easy access and use
Data Analysis	Analyzing data to derive insights and support decision-making
Business Planning	Supporting strategic and operational planning processes
Decision Making	Providing information and tools to aid in business decisions
Reporting	Generating reports for various stakeholders
Supply Chain Management	Managing the flow of goods, services, and information
Financial Management	Handling accounting, budgeting, and financial reporting
Human Capital Management	Managing employee-related processes and data
Procurement	Managing purchasing processes and supplier relationships
Clinical Operations*	Managing healthcare-specific processes (for healthcare organizations)
Artificial Intelligence Integration	Incorporating AI capabilities for advanced analytics and automation

Table 1: Main Functions of an ERP System

*Note: Clinical Operations is specific to healthcare organizations and may not be applicable to all ERP implementations.

Origins and Growth of SAP

Founded in Germany by former IBM Engineers, SAP ERP has its origins back in the 1970s. It launched one of the world's first enterprise-wide software systems creating integrated data visibility across diverse business functions.⁴

SAP ERP now has an enormous global footprint. SAP's ECC ERP system which emerged in 2004, has served as the vital digital backbone for countless enterprises across the world. However, this longstanding legacy system is now facing extinction - with SAP set to end support for ECC in 2027 as they urge

customers towards their next-generation S/4HANA platform. Experts advise advance planning and careful preparation to avoid hidden challenges.⁵

YEAR	EVENT
1970s	SAP founded
1992	SAP R/3 launched
2004	SAP ECC (Enterprise Central Component) introduced
2027	Planned end of mainstream support for SAP ECC
2030	SAP to support existing applications until this year for a fee

Table 2: SAP ERP Timeline

YEAR	NUMBER OF SAP CUSTOMERS
Mid-1990s	~2,000
Early 2000s	13,000+
Present day	440,000+ across 180 countries

Table 3: SAP Customer Growth Timeline

The predecessor to ECC, called SAP R/3, was launched in 1992 and already had a base of around 2,000 large clients by the mid-90s. This grew to 13,000+ by the early 2000s as ERP went mainstream. Today over 440,000 companies in over 180 countries use SAP software, with 77% of transaction revenue coming from outside Germany reflecting the huge global customer base across industries like manufacturing, consumer products, financial services and healthcare.

METRIC	VALUE
Countries using SAP software	180+
Companies using SAP software	440,000+
Named users working in SAP software	100+ million
SAP's annual revenues	Over €30 billion

Table 4: SAP by the Numbers

Globally SAP has 100+ million named users working regularly in its business software. ECC itself has tens of thousands of enterprise customers relying on it for mission critical functions. SAP's overall annual revenues are over €30 billion (2023)⁶ reflecting the giant scale of adoption. SAP core ERP like ECC, S/4HANA and related apps, databases and analytics account for over half the revenue.

Horses for Courses

There will always be the need to tailor solutions to the need of the organisation. One size never fits all. Every horse does not run well on every racecourse. Not everyone will need the vast library of SAP systems.⁷ So it is important that you take the time to understand what will work for you now, but also what will work in the future. There is a list of pre-project questions at the end of this paper, which you can build on to suit your needs, along with a table of challenges.

SAP is currently offering the NHS the advanced interoperability of SAP S/4HANA Cloud ERP, including clinical operations, supply chain management, Artificial Intelligence, spend management and human capital management etc. This has the additional purpose of helping the NHS join up its fragmented digital landscape.^{8 9} However, former NHS CIO Gartner health analyst Mike Jones believes that the days of all the huge EHR/EPR systems are coming to an end. He says that major ERP systems like Oracle and SAP are too closed and proprietary, for the emerging world of open platforms and data standards.¹⁰

The future answer for many organisations, may lie in a “mix” of systems or modules, configured according to requirements. For example, SAP Ariba is used for procurement by the NHS Shared Business Service or NHS-SBS. Ariba is a Cloud-based system, easily compatible with S/4HANA, which in turn can serve the wider enterprise.¹¹

SAP Ariba could be an ideal solution for an organisation who had used SAP Supplier Relationship Management (SAP SRM) with SAP ERP (ECC), for example. Syed Talal Hussain, a Product and Topic Expert with SAP, explains that S/4HANA Cloud is also integrated with SAP Business AI, providing an array of capabilities, including Advanced Predictive Analytics.¹²

The real “danger” ahead is for the large corporate SAP legacy systems whose time may be up sooner than expected. Important data may eventually be lost or become unusable, or the cost of recovery may then become prohibitive.

The Cliff Edge is Coming!

SAP ECC, is SAP's longtime ERP system that many large enterprises have relied on to run their business processes and operations. We have said that SAP S/4HANA is SAP's next-generation ERP suite that is meant to replace ECC eventually. It runs on the SAP HANA in-memory database and provides improved capabilities around analytics, flexibility, and integration. The SAP S/4HANA migration deadline refers to SAP's plan to end support for its older ERP system, ECC (ERP Central Component), by 2027.

The Problem Looms

In 2027, SAP plans to end mainstream maintenance and support for ECC. So, companies still on ECC need to migrate data and processes to S/4HANA well before then to avoid losing vendor support or to start facing higher costs for extended maintenance. Companies will want to avoid being caught without support for their critical ERP system. There is increased urgency and acceleration around S/4HANA migrations now, as the 2027 deadline approaches.

Diagram1: Projected SAP resource demand over the next 10 years
(Source: Stenzig. M., 2022) ¹³

However, migrating from ECC to S/4HANA is will likely be a major undertaking requiring extensive planning, evaluation, data migration, testing, training, etc. For many larger organisations, this could take years with huge costs and possible serious business disruptions, that could include substantial data losses.

Dilip Kumar Vaka of Deloitte Consulting (2024) discusses the importance of SAP S/4HANA migration for organizations seeking digital transformation and

operational excellence. In his “SAP S/4HANA Migration Roadmap”, he lists the key benefits of S/4HANA migration as including real-time insights and data processing, simplified user processes and interfaces, increased efficiency and automation, futureproofing with support for emerging technologies such as AI, and potential long-term cost savings.¹⁴

The 2027 ECC deadline is driving many SAP customers to undertake the significant initiative of transitioning to S/4HANA in the next few years!

What Happens Next?

Companies facing the S/4HANA migration deadline could face several serious implications if they don't complete the transition in time. These could include:

Operational Disruptions: Without ongoing vendor support for ECC past the deadline in 2027, companies may experience more frequent outages, bugs, or failures that they can't get promptly addressed or fixed. This could directly disrupt key business operations relying on the ERP system.

Compliance & Security Risks: They would also lose out on software patches, updates, and fixes related to compliance, security, or new regulations. This leaves them exposed on these fronts, open to potential cyber threats, fines or sanctions.

Higher Costs: Purchasing extended support or maintenance for ECC beyond 2027 will have increasing surcharges each year. Services and consulting help for unsupported software also tends to be much more expensive over time.

Difficulty With Innovation: Upgrading or extending an unsupported core ERP will only get more challenging and may require unreasonable customization. It could hinder you from tapping emerging options in AI, advanced analytics, etc.

Difficulty Attracting Talent: An organization still running highly outdated ECC in 2027 and beyond would appear outdated or rigid, struggling to attract talented IT and developers who want to work on modern platforms like S/4HANA or cloud systems.

Stifling of Agility & Growth: All of the above issues ultimately impact the business's bigger strategic goals, tie the organisation to aging legacy systems, and stifle their agility, scale, and growth potential.

The Final Transition

SAP is now in their final transition from legacy ERP to modular Cloud-based ERP solutions. This is an acknowledgement that traditional ERP systems no longer

meet modern business needs. While supporting existing applications until 2030, the company is focusing on its new, flexible, integrated, and modular solutions like S/4HANA to drive digital transformation.¹⁵

This strategic shift also represents a significant change for SAP, the long-time ERP leader and its customers. SAP is balancing its history with the evolving demands of the digital business era. However, with over 100 million users and tens of thousands of customers still reliant on SAP ECC today, this technology migration cliff edge presents an existential crisis for many organizations unprepared for the challenges of transitioning away from these legacy core systems.

Without the migration being done to plan and on time, core business agility, continuity and innovation are very much put at higher risk, especially past 2027, due to lack of support. The implications expand far beyond just technology alone but to all the value chains that the legacy SAP ECC still supports around the world.

CHALLENGE	DESCRIPTION
Complexity of existing IT landscapes	Integrating with multiple current/legacy systems
Data migration difficulties	Moving data from old to new system
Business process alignment	Adapting processes to new system capabilities
Custom coding adaptation	Modifying existing custom code for S/4HANA
Technical infrastructure requirements	Meeting new hardware/software needs
Integration with third-party systems	Ensuring compatibility with other software
Testing and validation	Ensuring system works as intended
Security and compliance concerns	Meeting regulatory and security standards
Resource constraints	Managing budget and personnel for the project

Table 4: Key Challenges in SAP S/4HANA Migration

According to Vaka (2024), some major challenges of migration include the complexity of existing IT landscapes, data migration difficulties and business process alignment. Others are custom coding (adaptation of existing bespoke code for S/4HANA), technical infrastructure requirements and integration with third-party systems. In addition, they mention potential challenges around testing and validation, security and compliance concerns, and of course, resource constraints.¹⁶

Vaka's (2024) paper, which is available on ResearchGate, is a must-read for IT Service Managers and others grappling with the SAP S/4HANA Migration and other major Digital Transformations.

Likely, most organisations will make the transition to S/4HANA before the deadline, and it is in the interest of SAP to offer them every help they can. It is however also likely that there could be some significant casualties who fall off the looming ECC to S/4HANA cliff edge, with some spectacular consequences.

The Way Forward

Here are some generic key questions that the C-Suite should ask the IT Department, Data Stewards, Data Owners, Operational and Change Managers, before starting the transition to SAP S/4HANA project. There are 9 key areas that you can refine or add to as needed:

1. Implementation strategy:

- What are our main challenges in implementing SAP S/4HANA?
- What strategies do we have in place to address these challenges?
- How will this implementation affect/improve our current business processes in general?

2. Performance improvements:

- What specific performance improvements can we expect from SAP S/4HANA compared to our current systems/processes?
- How will these improvements translate to business value?
- How will ongoing support be handled post-implementation?

3. Integration:

- How will SAP S/4HANA integrate with our other enterprise systems?
- How does this fit with our wider strategy for cloud integration?

4. Digital transformation:

- How does this transition align with our overall digital transformation strategies?
- What business processes will be most impacted by this change?

5. User experience and adoption:

- How does the user experience differ from our current system?

- What's our plan to ensure high adoption rates among our staff?
- What training programs will be put in place for our staff?
- Who has responsibility for the communications plan?

6. Legacy data management:

- What's our strategy for preserving and migrating our legacy data?
- How will we ensure no critical historical data is lost in the transition?

7. Cost and ROI:

- What's the total cost of ownership for this transition?
- How are we measuring the return on investment?
- Does it increase the ROI on our wider digital investment?

8. Timeline and resources:

- What's the proposed timeline for this transition?
- What resources (both human and financial) will be required?

9. Risk management:

- What are the main risks associated with this transition?
- How are we planning to mitigate these risks?

These questions should help managers gain a comprehensive understanding of the SAP S/4HANA transition process, its implications, and the necessary preparations, which should include a particular focus on preserving valuable legacy data.

There are also several companies like Avantra,¹⁷ as well as other Organizational Change Management (OCM) specialists like Oxford Global Resources,¹⁸ and Digivertex¹⁹ who will offer to help your organisation overcome your SAP S/4HANA transition challenges. It is well worth considering teaming up with a suitable implementation partner.

Conclusion

The transition from SAP's legacy ECC system to S/4HANA represents a critical juncture for organizations worldwide. With the 2027 deadline approaching, companies must act swiftly to avoid the risks associated with unsupported systems.

While the migration process is complex and challenging, it also presents opportunities for major digital transformation, improved business processes and a happier, more productive workforce. By asking the right questions, planning carefully, and partnering with experienced implementation specialists, organizations can navigate this transition successfully and position themselves for future growth and innovation in the digital future.

¹ Additional research for this paper was done using claude.ai

² Denecken, S., 2015, SAP S/4HANA - Frequently Asked Questions - Part 8 - 1511 update, <https://community.sap.com/t5/enterprise-resource-planning-blogs-by-sap/sap-s-4hana-frequently-asked-questions-part-8-1511-update/ba-p/13185131>, Accessed 13/07/2024.

³ <https://www.drink-it.com/inspiration/blog/which-erp-is-the-perfect-fit>, Accessed 13/07/2024

⁴ SAP: A 50-year history of success. <https://www.sap.com/about/company/history.html>, Accessed 12/07/2024

⁵ Stenzig, M., 2022, The impact of 2027 on SAP customers, <https://community.sap.com/t5/enterprise-resource-planning-blogs-by-members/the-impact-of-2027-on-sap-customers/ba-p/13525401>, Accessed 13/07/2024

⁶ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/263838/saps-global-revenue-since-2001/>, Accessed 13/07/2024

⁷ <https://www.worksmart.com/tailored-tech-solutions-a-game-changer>, Accessed 12/07/2024

⁸ <https://www.sap.com/uk/documents/2024/06/64f88a86-c27e-0010-bca6-c68f7e60039b.html>, Accessed 12/07/2024.

⁹ <https://www.sap.com/uk/industries/life-sciences-healthcare.html#products>, Accessed 12/07/2024.

¹⁰ Hoeksma, J., 2017, Gartner says NHS over-reliant on closed systems, <https://www.digitalhealth.net/2017/09/gartner-says-nhs-reliant-closed-systems>, Accessed 12/07/2024.

¹¹ https://www.sbs.nhs.uk/app/uploads/Introduction_to_SAP_with_NHS_SBS.pdf, Accessed 12/07/2024

¹² Hussain, S., 2024, Artificial Intelligence and Technologies in SAP S/4HANA Cloud Public Edition, <https://community.sap.com/t5/enterprise-resource-planning-blogs-by-sap/artificial-intelligence-and-technologies-in-sap-s-4hana-cloud-public/ba-p/13596117>, Accessed 12/07/2024

¹³ Diagram 1: Source: Stenzig, M., 2022, The impact of 2027 on SAP customers, <https://community.sap.com/t5/enterprise-resource-planning-blogs-by-members/the-impact-of-2027-on-sap-customers/ba-p/13525401>, Accessed 13/07/2024

¹⁴ Vaka, D., K., 2024, The SAP S/4HANA Migration Roadmap: From Planning to Execution, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/382062824_The_SAP_S4HANA_Migration_Roadmap_From_Planning_to_Execution, Accessed 13/07/2024.

¹⁵ Evans, B., 2021, SAP Buries the Past: Calls Out Legacy ERP, Welcomes Modular Cloud ERP, <https://accelerationeconomy.com/cloud/sap-buries-the-past-calls-out-legacy-erp-welcomes-modular-cloud-erp/#>, Accessed 12/07/2024

¹⁶ Vaka, D., K., 2024, The SAP S/4HANA Migration Roadmap: From Planning to Execution, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/382062824_The_SAP_S4HANA_Migration_Roadmap_From_Planning_to_Execution, Accessed 13/07/2024.

¹⁷ <https://www.avantra.com/blog/author/avantra-team>, Accessed 13/07/2024.

¹⁸ <https://www.oxfordcorp.com/en/insights/blog/sap-s-4hana-migration-implementations-overcoming-challenges-for-success>, Accessed 14/07/2024.

¹⁹ <https://digivertex.ltd>, Accessed 14/07/2024.